

Exploring the Factors Affecting to Adoption of Mobile Donation Applications in the Sri Lankan Community.

P.G.K.V. Gallage¹, C Ranil Peiris²

Department of Information Technology, Faculty of Management Studies and Commerce,
University of Sri Jayewardenepura, Gangodawila, Nugegoda, Sri Lanka,

gkaushi99@gmail.com, cranil@sjp.ac.lk

Introduction

Globalization and the development of technology have forced people to change various things in their lives. As an example, the trend of “going digital” makes people mainly depend on technology for their activities. It has an impact on various sectors, including education, health, charity work, entertainment, transportation, etc.

As a result of the development of technology, the world is unable to function without mobile phones. In 2021, Globally, there were 7.1 billion mobile subscribers, set to rise to 7.26 billion in 2022. Sri Lanka had 33.63 million mobile connections, with an average of 1.4 per individual from a total of 30.76 million devices (WorldData.Info, 2023). In general, mobile phones have changed how people live, work, and communicate with one another and have turned into an essential tool in many aspects of daily life. Mobile applications have a significant impact on users' lives and have enhanced global development, making the world a better place every day (Ang, 2014). They can be utilized in a variety of ways (Natarajan, et al., 2017)

Nowadays, poverty is a serious issue that affects practically every country. Lack of government assistance, job instability, unstable markets, food shortage and waste, nutritional quality, poor infrastructure, climate change, war and conflict, and discrimination are some of the major causes of poverty in the world. Today technology is advanced so there are technological solutions for every matter. As a suggestion solution for these poverty matters, build a relationship or a connection with the

person/country who is willing to support needy persons/countries by using technology. The presence, some countries use technology for donation-related activities, mobile donating applications, web-based donating systems, and Facebook social media apps have provided separate tabs for donation-related activities, currently, the globe is concerned with Utilizing technology for streamlined donation efforts. Examples from the real world GoFundMe - the form of online crowdfunding platforms, mobile applications, and social media integration, play a crucial role in enabling and enhancing donation-related activities on a global scale, American Red Cross Emergency App showcases the use of technology to enhance the efficiency, speed, and accessibility of donation-related activities during critical situations and Facebook Fundraisers have been instrumental in raising funds for medical expenses, disaster relief, educational initiatives, and more. The platform's massive user base and user-friendly interface have democratized fundraising, empowering individuals, and organizations to make a significant impact on a global scale.

Mobile donation apps are a quick and convenient method to help people, and there are a number of them available. (Ang, S., 2014, Shestakova, 2015) These applications appeal to researchers and practitioners because they develop valuable new strategies for building civic participation by exploiting the features of mobile applications (Garbett, et al., 2016) . Before creating a mobile application, developers should always consider a wide range of variables and make sure the app is appropriate for its intended use. (Chen, et al., 2019)The usability and satisfaction of donation applications(blood) are important factors in whether donors will use them and use them again for future donations. ((Batis & Albarrak, 2021) (Ouhbi, et al., 2015))However, there is still a few number of research on these modern forms of mobile donation platforms as a modern platform for technology-mediated civic involvement. (Choi & Kim, 2016)

Despite the growing popularity of mobile donation applications all over the world, mobile donation applications are a relatively new concept in Sri Lanka so the adoption of such applications in the Sri Lankan community remains relatively low rate. Therefore, need to understand the factors that

affect the adoption of mobile donation applications in the Sri Lankan community and understand why some people are hesitant to use them. Finding factors that affect the adoption of mobile donation app in Sri Lanka aids tailored app development and usage social development, strategies and benefiting economic in the country.

Research Question

This study focuses on finding answers to the, what are the factors that affect in Sri Lankan community to the adoption of mobile-based donation applications?

Research Objective

The objective of the study is to explore the factors that affect the adoption of the mobile donation application in the Sri Lankan Community.

Methodology

As the study intended to understand the causes affecting the adoption of mobile donation applications at the Sri Lankan community, inductive approach with a qualitative method was followed because in Sri Lankan context Mobile donation application concept is still new so the Quantitative approach is not suitable for collecting data for the study. Since this study is based on zero information respondents, non-probability sampling was used.

Eight semi-structured interviews were conducted. Interview questions were constructed based on

- Donation related information,
- Mobile Phone Behavioural and
- Mobile Donation Application related information.

The participants of this study were donors, volunteers, and employees of charity organizations and persons who have income sources. Table 1:

Participant Demographics provides a summary of demographics and background of the participants.

Table 1: Participant Demographics

ID	AGE	GENDER	CITY	ROLE	STATUS
P1	57	Male	Kandy	Retired Airforce Officer	Married
P2	30	Male	Mount Lavinia	Quality Checker	Married
P3	23	Female	Colombo	Marketing	Single
P4	27	Female	Mount Lavinia	IT Teacher	Married
P5	32	Female	Nugegoda	IT Audit Senior Manager	Single
P6	28	Female	Kadawatha	Accountant	Married
P7	48	Female	Kandy	Senior assistant Secretary	Married
P8	23	Male	Pita Kotte	Photographer	Single

To analyse the gathered data from the study, an inductive thematic analysis approach was undertaken.

Results and Discussion

This research helped identify factors that affecting to the adoption of the mobile donation application in Sri Lankan community. The findings indicate that perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, social influence, trust and security awareness and knowledge and technology accessibility are significant motivators for adopting mobile donation applications. The

above findings are similar to the key components of the Technology acceptance model ,Technology Acceptance model (TAM) is mainly used theoretical framework is the field of information systems and technology management. (MediaWiki, 7 January 2024) However, concerns trust and security, lack of awareness and knowledge, technology matters and preference for traditional donation method(social and security issues) serve as barriers to adoption. The list of codes and themes discovered throughout the analysis, together with their frequency of occurrence, are shown below.

Table 2:Code Frequency

Category	Theme	Code	Count	Cases
Positive factors consider before use the mobile donation applications	User Acceptance Factors	Perceived Usefulness	1	1
	User Acceptance Factors	Perceived Ease of Use	14	7
	User Acceptance Factors	Awareness and Knowledge	1	1
	Social and Cultural factors	Social Influence	1	1
	Technological Factors	Technology Accessibility	7	5
	Trust and Security factors	Security	13	7
	Trust and Security factors	Trust	6	5
Barriers and challengers to prevent using mobile donation application	User Acceptance Factors	Lack of Awareness and Knowledge	3	3
	Social and Culture factors	Social and religion issues	5	4
	Technological Factors	Technology matters	4	4
	Trust and Security factors	Security issues	4	4
	Trust and Security factors	Trust Issues	6	5

Figure 1:Thematic map

	Motivating factors
	Barriers and challengers

Conclusion

Implications

The findings of this study provide an impressive amount of information and insights about the mobile donation adoption by Sri Lankan community, thereby filling the theoretical gap in the context and help developing a preliminary understanding about the topic. The theoretical contributions of the study are understanding the technology acceptability, social influence, trust and perceived risk will be improved by. Also from a practical perspective, findings of this research would be in use when trying to introduce and enhance the mobile donation application into Sri Lankan context.

Research limitations and future research suggestions

In this study there are several limitations, small sample size, technology barriers and limited scope were the major limitations.

As recommendations for future research, conducting large scale surveys to collect quantitative data to conduct a quantitative approach that test a theoretical model developed with the identified positive and negative factors.

References

1. Afaf Ali Batis & Ahmed Albarrak, 2021. Preferences and features of a blood donation smartphone app: A multicenter mixed-methods study in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. Volume 1.
2. Ang, S., 2014. *6 Apps That Fit Charity Into Your Daily Routine*, s.l.: s.n.
3. Boreum Choi & Mingyung Kim, 2016. Donation via Mobile Applications: A Study of the Factors Affecting Mobile Donation Application Use. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, Volume 32.

4. Chen, J., Tran, A. & Nguyen, T., 2019. Understanding the discontinuance behavior of mobile shoppers as a consequence of technostress: An application of the stress-coping theory. *Computers in Human Behavior*, Volume 95, pp. 83-95.
5. Garbett, . A. et al., 2016. App Movement: A Platform for Community Commissioning of Mobile Applications.
6. MediaWiki, 7 January 2024. *Technology acceptance model*. [Online]
Available at:
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Technology_acceptance_model
7. Natarajan, Thamaraiselvan & Balasubramanian, Senthil Arasu & Kasilingam, Dharun Lingam, 2017. Understanding the intention to use mobile shopping applications and its influence on price sensitivity. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Elsevier, Volume vol. 37(C), pp. pages 8-22..
8. Ouhbi, et al., 2015. Compliance of blood donation apps with mobile OS usability guidelines. Volume 39.
9. WorldData.Info, 2023. *WorldData.info*. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.worlddata.info/asia/sri-lanka/telecommunication.php>